

Canada Research Chair in Media, Disabilities and (Self) Representations

Questionnaire Character

Linked to the Disability and Deafhood Database
chairemediashandicaps.uqam.ca/database/

PURPOSE OF THE CRCMHA

IDENTIFY groups living with one or more disabilities that are predominantly represented in the Canadian media (1980-2020) as well as the characteristics of these (self)representations, the characters represented and their authors;

To better UNDERSTAND the relation between contemporary media representations of disability (2000-2020) and their uses by people with disabilities;

Determine measures likely to IMPROVE over time the presence and inclusion of people with disabilities in media content through the development and implementation of inclusive "media policies" promoting the full social participation of the groups concerned.

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UQÀM | **Chaire de recherche du Canada
sur les médias, les handicaps
et les (auto)représentations**
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Canada Research
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Canada

1) Name of character

Open data

2) Episode(s) during which character is present (television series) (French)

Open data

2B) Episode(s) during which character is present (television series) (English)

Open data

3) Character type

Closed data / Multiple choice

Human
Humanoid / Robot
Animal
Other

Type of disability (character) (Statistics Canada)

4) Sensory disability

Check box

5) Physical disability

Check box

6) Pain-related disability

Check box

7) Mental health-related disability

Check box

8) Cognitive disability

Check box

9) Unknown disability

Check box

10) Neurodivergent character

Check box

10B) Deaf character

Character has a disability that impacts

11) Assuming responsibilities

Check box

12) Communicating / Expressing themselves

Check box

13) Carrying out personal care

Check box

14) Maintaining their living environment

Check box

15) Getting around (outside the home)

Check box

16) Feeding themselves

Check box

17) Type of disability / disabling situation of character (details)

Open data

18) Feigned or real disability

Closed data / Multiple choice

Feigned
Real

19) Character hides their disability or disabilities

Check box

20) Origin of character's disability

Closed data / Multiple choice

Caused wilfully (by others)
Due to age
Due to an accident
Due to an illness
From birth
Unknown
Multiple
Other

21) Character acquires one or more disabilities during the story

Check box

22) How character discovers their disability

Closed data / Multiple choice

Due to the difficulty or impossibility of doing something
Via a member of the medical profession
Via the surrounding characters
Visible disability
Discovery of disability not shown
Discovery of disability in past
Other

23) Character discloses their disability to other characters in the story

Check box

24) Character experiences anger in relation to their disability or disabling situation

Check box

25) Age of character

Closed data / Multiple choice

Child
Teenager
Young adult
Adult
Elder
More than one answer / Other

26) Age of character (details)

Open data

27) Gender identity of character (inferred)

Closed data / Multiple choice

Genderqueer
Man
Non-binary
Woman

28) Gender modality of character (inferred)

Closed data / Multiple choice

Cisgender
Transgender

29) Presence of issues related to character's gender

Check box

30) Sexual orientation (represented) of character

Closed data / Multiple choice

Asexual
Bisexual
Gay
Heterosexual
Lesbian
Pansexual
Queer
Two-spirited
Indeterminate / Undeclared

31) Character has erotic desires, dreams and/or fabrications

Check box

32) Character has sexual relationship(s)

Check box

33) Main civil status of character

Closed data / Multiple choice

Single
Dating
Common-law partner
Married
Separated
Divorced
Widowed
Changes during the story
Other
Unknown

34) Main civil status of character (details) (French)

Open data

34B) Main civil status of character (details) (English)

Open data

35) Character has sexual or romantic relationship(s) with another character who is neurodivergent and/or Deaf and/or has a disability

Check box

36) Presence of issues related to character's parenthood

Check box

37) Presence of issues related to character's ethnocultural origins

Check box

38) Character belongs to a visible minority

Check box

39) Character identifies as Indigenous

Check box

40) Economic class of character

Closed data / Multiple choice

Underprivileged
Middle class
Upper class
Pretends to be in another social class
Changes during the story
Unknown

41) Main occupation of the character when they have a disability

Closed data / Multiple choice

Accounting
Administrative support and office work
Advertising

CRCMHA - Questionnaire - Character

Agriculture / Forestry
Arts
Biopharmaceutical
Communications
Construction
Documentation
Education
Engineering
Executive / Senior management
Fashion
Film / Television / Radio
Finance / Real estate
Food services
Healthcare
Hospitality
Human resources and industrial relations
Information technology (IT) / Multimedia
Insurance
Law and trades related to public protection
Leisure industry
Maintenance and upkeep
Organized crime
Production / Handling
Religion
Sales and customer service
Science
Social services
Tourism
Trade and various services
Transportation / Heavy equipment operation
Unknown
None
In school
Not applicable

42) Character changes profession or stops practicing their profession because of one or more disabilities

Check box

43) Profession (details)

Open data

44) Presence of religious issues (religion, beliefs, spirituality, etc.)

Check box

Character has a hobby or leisure activity

45) Cerebral / Intellectual

Check box

46) Creative
Check box

47) Physical
Check box

48) Social / Community-based
Check box

49) Other
Check box

50) Hobby / Leisure (details) (French)
Open data

50B) Hobby / Leisure (details) (English)
Open data

51) Character engages in social or group activities
Check box

Context(s) in which character evolves

52) Employment / Work / Volunteering
Check box

53) Family
Check box

54) Living environment (medical and social institutions)
Check box

55) Pedagogy / Educational system
Check box

56) Interpersonal relationships
Check box

57) Services
Check box

58) Transportation and public space
Check box

59) Neighbourhood
Check box

60) Character is a source of conflict
Check box

Type of support received by the character

61) Technical support
Check box

62) Layout
Check box

63) Human support

Check box

64) Animal support

Check box

65) Character uses a professional interpreter

Check box

66) Character uses sexual assistance

Check box

67) Character uses psychosocial support services

Check box

68) Character uses a pharmaceutical aid related to a disability or disabling situation

Check box

69) Character has a physical addiction to a substance or substances (e.g., alcohol, drugs, tobacco, etc.)

Check box

Character experiences

70) ableism

Check box

71) racism

Check box

72) sexism

Check box

73) ageism

Check box

74) intimidation

Check box

75) violence

Check box

76) abuse

Check box

77) Character fights for their rights

Check box

78) Presence of dream or imagined scenes where character is shown without disability or disabling situation

Check box

79) Production presents a spectacularization of disability (crisis, etc.)

Check box

80) Production presents a distinctive visual and/or sound treatment of disability

Open data

81) Type of role

Closed data / Multiple choice

Main
Secondary
Tertiary

82) Main diegetic role

Closed data / Multiple choice

Ally
Antihero
Hero
Mentor
Opponent / Adversary
Victim
Villain
Other
Multiple roles
Not applicable

83) Character has suicidal thoughts

Check box

84) Character tries to take their own life

Check box

85) Character dies during the story

Closed data / Multiple choice

Accidental death
Due to illness
Murder
Natural death
Suicide
Assisted suicide
Unknown cause
Other
Planned death
Not applicable

86) Name of performer

Open data

Type of disability (performer) (Statistics Canada)

87) Sensory disability

Check box

88) Physical disability

Check box

89) Pain-related disability

Check box

90) Mental health-related disability

Check box

91) Cognitive disability

Check box

92) Unknown disability

Check box

93) Performer is neurodivergent

Check box

93B) Performer is Deaf

Check box

94) Notes on character

Open data

95) Problems with character

Open data